

Deliverable D1.4 Sustainability Strategy

Project Title	Founding a Global Image Data Ecosystem
Project Acronym	FoundingGIDE
Project Number	101130216
Project Start Date	01.01.2024
Project Duration	30 Months

WP Number & Title	WP1: Project management, dissemination and long-term sustainability
WP Leaders	EURO-BIOIMAGING
Deliverable Lead Beneficiary	3-EMBL
Dissemination Level	PU - Public
Deliverable type	R — Document, report
Contractual Delivery Date	30.06.2026
Actual Delivery Date	30.06.2026
Authors	Aastha Mathur
Contributors	
Reviewers	Sudeep Das, Maria Mirza

Change Log

Version	Date	Author	Description of changes
v0.1	22.06.2026	Aastha Mathur	Initial draft
final	29.06.2026	Aastha Mathur	Final

Acronyms and Abbreviations

BIA	BiImage Archive
-----	-----------------

EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FBbi	Biological Imaging Methods Ontology
GerBI	German BioImaging
GIDE	Global Image Data Ecosystem
IDR	Image Data Resource
PRISM	PReclinical Imaging Standardized Metadata
RI	Research Infrastructure
RO-Crate	Research Object Crate
SSBD	A platform for Systems Science of Biological Dynamics
XNAT	Extensible Neuroimaging Archive Toolkit

Table of contents

Acronyms and Abbreviations	2
Table of contents	3
Executive Summary	4
1. Introduction	5
2. Description of assets	5
2.1. Bioluminescence assets	6
2.2. Preclinical assets	6
2.2. Community assets	6
3. Scope of sustenance activities	6
3.1. Goals	7
3.2. Needs and strategy	7
4. Mechanisms for governance and collaborations	7
4.1. GIDE:Bioluminescence	7
4.1.1 Scope	7
4.1.2 Partners	7
4.1.3 Initial governance procedures	8
4.2. GIDE:Preclinical	8
4.2.1 Scope	8
4.2.2 Partners	8
4.2.3 Initial procedures	8
4.3. GIDE:Community	8
4.3.1 Scope	8
4.3.2 Partners	8
4.3.3 Initial procedures	9
4.4. Coordination of GIDE	9
4.4.1 Scope	9
4.4.2 Partners	9
4.4.3 Initial governance and procedures	10
5. Pathways to growth and inclusion	10
6. Conclusion and Next Steps	10

Executive Summary

The foundingGIDE project has brought together imaging research and data infrastructures from across the globe to lay strong foundations towards image data sharing. A key measure of project success is the partners' commitment towards sustainability of the project outputs based on fruitful collaborations enabled under the foundingGIDE project. This commitment is critical for the imaging and wider scientific community as the project outputs are deemed extremely relevant for building a global image data sharing infrastructure in future. This deliverable details the output of the project that will be maintained by partners beyond the end of the project itself, as well as an outlook towards future growth to extend project activities. The benefits of the foundingGIDE project will hence be felt beyond the project lifetime fueling a future Global Image Data Ecosystem (GIDE).

1. Introduction

foundingGIDE project has, over its 30-month duration (Jan 2024-June 2026), established a strong foundation of a Global Image Data Ecosystem to enable federated search across multiple distinct open bioimage data resources. These achievements are a result of strong technical advancements and community building efforts. On the technical side, the project has developed the GIDE stack, comprising a federated search portal over four databases (BioImage Archive, Image Data Resource (IDR), SSBD Database and SSBD Repository), a shared core metadata model (GIDE-REMBI), a detached Research Object Crate (RO-Crate) interchange profile (GIDE RO-Crate) and an indexing infrastructure. Additionally, the project partners have decided on FBbi ontology to become the default ontology for bioimaging and have taken over its maintenance. Project partners have also provided recommendations to adopt preclinical imaging ontologies based on community surveys and elaborated the PRISM (PREclinical Imaging Standardized Metadata) model to describe the complete lifecycle of a preclinical imaging study aiming to improve federated searchability of preclinical images across XNAT nodes. To strengthen the impact and uptake of the technical outputs, the project has consolidated a diverse community of Research Infrastructures (RIs), imaging networks, imaging core facilities, thematic groups etc., and disseminated project outputs to global stakeholders including, researchers, policy makers, funders and industry partners. All the project objectives have been achieved and various impact measures have exceeded what was originally planned in the grant proposal.

2. Description of assets

The primary outcomes of foundingGIDE, shown in Figure 1, were produced during the project lifetime. The technical components, that have been developed as a proof of concept, are now being accepted as recommendations for the global community to align with, enabling machine actionability for imaging data use and re-use. Moreover, the global stakeholders are now more aware of GIDE and its objective which will make future activities around global image data sharing more pronounced and facilitate update and extension by the community.

Figure 1: Key outcomes of the foundingGIDE project

The combination of these outputs, and their individual importance for imaging, wider life science and data research puts foundingGIDE in a central position among research community as well as

policy stakeholders. The outputs have been split into modular components, which allow for focussed maintenance plans and structured growth for future developments.

2.1. BioImaging assets

Major technical components from foundingGIDE project, relevant for the bioimaging community are listed below:

- Ontology recommendation and maintenance: [D2.1](#), D5.1 and D5.2
- GIDE RO-Crate Profile: <https://www.gide-project.org/ro-crate/search/1.0/profile>
- GIDE Search: <https://github.com/foundingGIDE/gide-search>
- GIDE API infrastructure: <https://www.gide-project.org/search/search>

2.2. Preclinical assets

The technical components from foundingGIDE project, relevant for the preclinical community are listed below:

- Ontology recommendations [D4.1](#)
- Preclinical imaging standardized metadata (PRISM) D8.1
- Preclinical metadata workflows and tools D12.1

2.3. Community assets

foundingGIDE project has built a strong, active and visible community around open image data sharing. The relevant mechanisms and scale of community outreach are listed below:

- Webpage: a branded, visible webpage, hosted by Euro-BioImaging, that enables dissemination of project outputs and events, as well as relevant information materials on image data sharing for the wider community. (Scale: more than 1900 visits)
- Newsletter: Compact, curated and easy to grasp information materials produced quarterly by the partners to disseminate project outputs and relevant information from partners and community. (Scale: Around 380 subscribers to the GIDE newsletter)
- Social media: branded professional social media, LinkedIn, presence of the project to disseminate project outcomes and engage with relevant stakeholders. (Scale: Over 500 followers on LinkedIn)
- Collection of project outputs: Deliverables, event summaries and presentations, workshop and training materials available via open resources, like GIDE [community page on Zenodo](#) and video materials on [Euro-BioImaging YouTube Channel](#)
- Technical Community Liaison: Identified individuals from within and outside the project to interact with technical communities like, OME, vEM, QuarepLiMi, EDAM BioImaging, RO-Crate, etc. (Scale: Over 20 communities reached)
- Visibility on EU RI and policy landscape: Visibility of the project outcomes across Euro-BioImaging Nodes, as well as across European and national policy initiatives, like ESFRI, EOSC, NFDI etc.

3. Scope of sustenance activities

foundingGIDE project has identified outputs which are essential assets for the community to build common image data sharing solutions on. It has identified pathways for ensuring that the assets are

maintained in a minimal viable form, based on partners' commitments. These activities will ensure availability of project's key results to all stakeholders beyond the end of the project lifetime, while future mid and longer term maintenance and development will need dedicated funding.

3.1. Goals

The common goal of the partners is to maintain the availability of GIDE infrastructure and the visibility of the GIDE community such that the global stakeholders can continue to leverage foundingGIDE outputs beyond project lifetime, while maintaining project internal collaborations to improve readiness towards any future opportunities for further development.

3.2. Needs and strategy

The maintenance of project outputs requires resources beyond those made available during the foundingGIDE project. The importance of foundingGIDE project outputs and the general alignment of the projects' objectives with those of the partners' has been leveraged to ensure availability of these outputs through in-kind contributions from the project partners. While these activities will be currently covered by each individual partner themselves, efforts will be made to identify future funding opportunities to grow this inclusive ecosystem. The current framework for collaboration can hence be interpreted as a *coalition of the willing*.

4. Mechanisms for governance and collaborations

The combination of technical and community outputs from foundingGIDE will have parallel maintenance mechanisms to ensure alignment with individual partners' needs, reduce overhead to minimal, and maintain agility in developments, as the nature of the activities themselves are varied. A common GIDE Governance Framework will be defined as a non-binding agreement to establish governance bodies with partner representation for high level coordination of GIDE activities and to mediate interactions across streams.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of GIDE Governance Framework

4.1. GIDE:BioImaging

To ensure continued availability of the bioimaging federated search infrastructure, relevant partners are establishing a lightweight interim governance arrangement to keep the technical product working while allowing controlled growth.

4.1.1 Scope

GIDE:BioImaging covers maintenance processes for the following components:

- GIDE federated search
- GIDE-REMBI
- GIDE RO-Crate
- The FBbi ontology
- Indexing/search/API stack

4.1.2 Partners

Following are the relevant partners for GIDE:BioImaging:

- RIKEN: operates SSBD:database and SSBD:repository
- EMBL-EBI: operates the BioImage Archive; hosts IDR infrastructure
- GerBI / Dundee teams: operate IDR (includes partner beyond foundingGIDE project for effective implementation)
- Euro-BioImaging: coordinates GIDE activities and cross-stream and community engagement

4.1.3 Initial governance procedures

A lightweight interim governance arrangement has been established and agreed upon by the partners to continue essential activities beyond June 2026, with technical decision making through consensus between RIKEN, EMBL-EBI and GerBI/Dundee teams, and additional resource onboarding mediated by Euro-BioImaging. The governance arrangement will be made openly available (upon official partner agreement and within the year 2026) to the public to inform them of the transparent processes of GIDE:BioImaging infrastructure and the underlying decision making. The maintenance plan for FBbi Ontology is described in Deliverable 5.2. GIDE:BioImaging¹ will be represented within the GIDE Governance Framework.

4.2. GIDE:Preclinical

The partners will ensure maintenance of the preclinical ontology recommendations based on community input and the PRISM metadata model. The implementation of the PRISM model in the PIDAR database has been a key tangible output for the preclinical imaging community.

4.2.1 Scope

GIDE:Preclinical covers maintenance processes for the following component:

- Preclinical imaging ontology recommendations
- PRISM metadata model

4.2.2 Partners

Following are the relevant partners for GIDE:Preclinical:

- CNR: developing community ontology recommendations and PRISM metadata model
- NIF: Supporting the preclinical ontology recommendations and metadata model
- RIKEN: Supporting the preclinical ontology recommendations and metadata model

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20807424>

4.2.3 Initial procedures

The partners aim to update ontology recommendations, together with initiatives like ESMI, elaborate processes for PRISM model update and implement the recommendations in the PIDAR metadata repository to make them available to the users. GIDE:preclinical will encompass these activities.

4.3. GIDE:Community

The maintenance of branding and visibility of the project, mediation of community interactions, and continued dissemination of current project results and future project related outcomes are essential to sustain the interest of the foundingGIDE community that has been built over the past 2.5 years.

4.3.1 Scope

GIDE:Community covers continuation of the following activities:

- Outreach: This includes website, newsletter and social media presence
- Dissemination: Involvement of imaging core facilities, including Euro-BioImaging Nodes
- Integration into Operations: This includes implementation of GIDE outputs eg, in Euro-BioImaging Access Portal, and adopting GIDE recommendations
- Mediate GIDE interaction with external entities
- Training and capacity building

4.3.2 Partners

All foundingGIDE partners are relevant partners for GIDE:Community:

- Euro-BioImaging: mediating external representation, community interactions across Nodes and national data sharing initiatives, and implementing exemplary foundingGIDE outputs on Euro-BioImaging Access Portal
- Global BioImaging: mediating community interactions across and beyond foundingGIDE partners extending the to the global imaging community
- NIF: providing training and outreach materials for GIDE:Preclinical.
- Microscopy Australia: mediating community interactions within Australian context
- CNR: providing training and outreach materials for GIDE:Preclinical
- RIKEN: providing training and outreach materials for GIDE:BioImaging and GIDE:Preclinical
- EMBL EBI: providing training and outreach materials for GIDE:BioImaging
- GerBI: providing training and outreach materials for GIDE:BioImaging

4.3.3 Initial procedures

GIDE:Community efforts are collaborative dissemination actions based on existing networks and relevant groups within foundingGIDE partners. These will be leveraged to promote dissemination of project outputs, initiate any new project adjacent activities, promote any cross partner exchange of experience, etc. In the current form, any new actions will follow the same processes as those established during foundingGIDE (i.e. by involving communication partners with relevant technical teams). As a controlled number of new partners will join the activities in future, a GIDE Community Board will be established under the GIDE governance framework to maintain coherence in messaging across the broad community base as well as to ensure a balanced community representation.

4.4. Coordination of GIDE

Coordination among the parallel streams and presenting a common front for external interaction will be key to consolidate current foundingGIDE efforts and strategically extend GIDE in future.

4.4.1 Scope

GIDE:Coordination covers continuation of the following activities:

- Ensure essential coordination across streams and revolve dependencies and enable fruitful collaboration among current partners, as and when required.
- Presenting a common front for collaborative activities towards external partners
- Representing GIDE strategically in EU landscape
- Scoping for future funding

4.4.2 Partners

All foundingGIDE partners are relevant partners for GIDE:Coordination:

- Euro-Biolmaging: mediates cross-stream interactions, represents GIDE in the EU Research Infrastructure (RI) landscape and supports alignment with EU policy agendas relevant to RIs, Open Science, FAIR data and international cooperation.
- EMBL-EBI
- GerBI
- RIKEN
- CNR
- NIF
- Microscopy Australia
- Global Biolmaging

All partners are represented in GIDE:Coordination to cover technical and community representation.

4.4.3 Initial governance and procedures

GIDE:Coordination will be managed by Euro-Biolmaging. A GIDE:Coordination board will be established with representation from each foundingGIDE partner to ensure all partners maintain collaborations and are informed of relevant high level decisions, interactions, strategic representation and potential funding opportunities around GIDE. The board will meet at least quarterly at the end of the project. The frequency can be adjusted upon need, as determined by the partners. GIDE:Coordination board will be part of the general GIDE Governance Framework.

5. Pathways to growth and inclusion

A strong motivation to continue basic activities around foundingGIDE outputs is the community interest in continued targeted dissemination, interactions, collaborations, and future inclusion into the Global Image Data Ecosystem (GIDE). The foundingGIDE partners deem such high interest as a sign of community need and project success, and are committing to supporting future activities in-kind, within limited capacity, as described above. Current sustainability activities already include controlled amounts of new activities, like potential new database indexing, outreach activities in upcoming events, etc. More extensive developments, both technically, towards community growth, as well as for robust governance, however, need additional resources. While the current

sustainability processes are already described with potential extension in mind, the partners are also actively identifying funding sources to carry out advanced activities towards growing an inclusive GIDE.

6. Conclusion and Next Steps

As the very successful foundingGIDE project reaches the end of its lifetime in June 2026, the highly active project partners are looking forward to continuing development and engaging with a wider bioimaging community, by maintaining basic GIDE activities. The governance framework around these continued activities are being formulated as a non-binding agreement that will be agreed upon by project partners to formalise the collaboration in its current form until either it is superseded by a formal governance framework (e.g. through a successful follow-on grant) or replaced by explicit agreement of the partners. The governance framework will be reviewed 12 months after the end of the project.